

Universitat de Barcelona
Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional

REPOSITORY PRACTICES:
Tutorial for Zenodo Platform

SOUZA, J. R.

December, 2024

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1 Signing up and Logging in

First step consist of creating an account to have access to the platform. To do so, you must copy and paste the following website address in your browser:

<https://zenodo.org/>

which will guide you to the following screen:

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo on the left, a search bar, and links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. On the right side of the navigation bar, there are 'Log in' and 'Sign up' buttons. A red arrow points to the 'Sign up' button. Below the navigation bar, there is a 'Featured communities' section with a slider. The current community shown is the 'Biodiversity Literature Repository', which is described as 'A community to share publications related to bio-systematics.' Below this, there is a 'Recent uploads' section listing three items: a presentation on 'Datenerhebungen in Zukunftsthemen des Bildungsmonitorings', a presentation on 'DataCite Infrastructure & FAIR principles', and a dataset on 'Cuestionarios y bases de datos del proyecto "La orientación de los centros de transfusión de sangre españoles"'. To the right of the 'Recent uploads' section, there is a 'Why use Zenodo?' section with a list of benefits, and a 'Newsletter' sign-up form.

Click on the orange little box in the upper right corner where is written "Sign up". It takes you to the subscription page. If you prefer, it is possible to create a Zenodo account using **GitHub**, **ORCID** or **OpenAIRE** already existing account. To do so, simply choose one of that options by clicking on the corresponding field. Otherwise, you must fill the fields:

USERNAME, FULLNAME, AFFILIATIONS, EMAIL, PASSWORD

Then, click on the orange box ("Sign up") to create an account.

zenodo

Research. Shared! Sign up today

Citeable. Discoverable
Uploads get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to make them easily and uniquely citeable.

Communities
Accept or reject uploads to your own community (e.g. workshops, EU projects, institutions or entire disciplines).

Trusted Research Data Management
Built on top of CERN's expertise in managing 100s of petabytes of research data from the Large Hadron Collider.

Sign up with GitHub
Sign up with ORCID
Sign up with OpenAIRE

— OR —

USERNAME
FULL NAME
AFFILIATIONS
EMAIL ADDRESS

Sign up

Already have an account? Log in
Privacy notice

OpenAIRE CERN European Union

After registering on the platform, you will receive a verification email from Zenodo. Follow the link in the email to confirm your subscription. Once your account is verified, you must log in to access the platform. Again, on the Zenodo home page click on the white box written "Log in".

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard Log in Sign up

Featured communities

Biodiversity Literature Repository Browse
A community to share publications related to bio-systematics.

Recent uploads

December 5, 2024 (1.0) Presentation Open
Datenerhebungen in Zukunftsthemen des Bildungsmonitorings. Herangehensweisen für die kommunale Beratung
Weydert, Daniel; Förster, André
Der Vortrag thematisiert, wie Kommunen darin unterstützt werden können, eigene Datenerhebungen für ein thematisch fokussiertes Bildungsmonitoring (z. B. der Bildung für nachhaltige Entwicklung oder politischen und kulturellen Bildung) zu entwickeln und umzusetzen. Anhand von wissenschaftlich-methodischen Standards sowie Praxisbeispielen aus den...
Uploaded on December 5, 2024
Part of Fachstelle Kommunales Bildungsmonitoring (KOSMO)

December 5, 2024 (v1) Presentation Open
DataCite Infrastructure & FAIR principles
Mejias, Gabriela; Hirsch, Mary; Chen, Xiaoli
This presentation was shared during a webinar for the Belnet community.
Uploaded on December 5, 2024
Part of DataCite

December 5, 2024 (v1) Dataset Open
Cuestionarios y bases de datos del proyecto "La orientación de los centros de transfusión de sangre españoles hacia sus principales stakeholders desde una perspectiva de capital social y su influencia en la performance" (ORCETRASA-ECO2015-64875-R)
Martín-Santana, Josefa D.; Beerli-Palacio, Asunción; Cabrera-Suárez, M. Katiuska
Este dataset está compuesto por dos cuestionarios (formato .pdf) y dos bases de datos (formato .csv). El fichero "CUESTIONARIO DONANTES PROYECTO ORCETRASA", que consta de 26 preguntas y cuyas respuestas se corresponden con las columnas de la base de datos "BASE DONANTES PROYECTO ORCETRASA". Y el fichero "CUESTIONARIO CENTROS PROYECTO...
Uploaded on December 5, 2024
Part of University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria

Why use Zenodo?

- **Safe** — your research is stored safely for the future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists.
- **Trusted** — built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE to ensure that everyone can join in Open Science.
- **Citeable** — every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), to make them citable and trackable.
- **No waiting time** — Uploads are made available online as soon as you hit publish, and your DOI is registered within seconds.
- **Open or closed** — Share e.g. anonymized clinical trial data with only medical professionals via our restricted access mode.
- **Versioning** — Easily update your dataset with our versioning feature.
- **GitHub integration** — Easily preserve your GitHub repository in Zenodo.
- **Usage statistics** — All uploads display standards compliant usage statistics

Newsletter

Receive updates on our latest developments, projects and upcoming webinars sent quarterly.

E-mail *
your-email@example.com

Name
Your name

Subscribe

Then, fill your credentials **EMAIL ADDRESS** and **PASSWORD** to get it logged.

The image shows the Zenodo login interface. At the top, the Zenodo logo is displayed in white on a blue background. Below the logo is a white box titled "Log in to account". Inside this box, there are three buttons for social login: "Sign in with ORCID", "Sign in with GitHub", and "Sign in with OpenAIRE". Below these buttons is the text "OR". Underneath "OR" is a red-bordered box containing the login form. The form has two input fields: "EMAIL ADDRESS" and a password field (indicated by dots). Below the password field is a "Log in" button. At the bottom of the white box, there are links for "New to Zenodo? Sign up", "Privacy notice", "Forgot password?", and "Resend confirmation email".

2 Uploading files

To upload some file while in your home page on Zenodo platform, you must click on the white plus sign upper right, and then click on "New upload".

The screenshot displays the Zenodo homepage. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for "Communities" and "My dashboard". A red arrow points to a white plus sign in the top right corner, which has opened a dropdown menu with options for "New upload" and "New community". Below the navigation bar, the "Featured communities" section highlights the "Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI)". The "Recent uploads" section lists three items: a poster from October 28, 2024, a presentation from October 17, 2024, and another presentation from October 17, 2024. On the right side, there is a "Why use Zenodo?" section with a list of benefits and a "Newsletter" sign-up form.

zenodo Search records... Communities My dashboard + rosadesou...
New upload
New community

Featured communities

Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) Browse

Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) aims to develop collaborative approaches for data management and sharing through inclusion of the generalist repositories in the NIH data ecosystem.

Recent uploads

October 28, 2024 (v1) Poster Open

Constraining CMIP6 simulations for the deep Arctic using an AMOC-SST index - poster at DMI Climate Science Symposium 2024

Devillers, Marion; Olsen, Steffen Malskaer; Langehaug, Helene Reinertsen

Poster presented at the Climate Science Symposium in Copenhagen, Denmark. Abstract: The AtlanticWater (AW) plays a key role regarding the future changes in the Arctic ocean, as it transports salt and heat within the Arctic Ocean basins. The recent increase in poleward ocean heat transport is not always well-captured by climate models which...

Uploaded on December 5, 2024
Part of EU Open Research Repository, ObsSea4Clim

October 17, 2024 (v1) Presentation Open

From Climate Science to Decision-making: how policymakers and final users can benefit from research outcomes - OBPS workshop

Salge, Paula

Presentation delivered at Ocean Best Practices Workshop, online, on 17 October 2024. Part of the session "Ocean-Climate Nexus - Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points, and the downstream effects of Tipping Points." organized jointly by TipESM, OCEAN:ICE, ClimTip and ObsSea4Clim EU Horizon projects.

Uploaded on December 5, 2024
Part of EU Open Research Repository, ObsSea4Clim

October 17, 2024 (v1) Presentation Open

Understanding the tipping points - what are the challenges? - OBPS workshop

Swingedouw, Didier

Presentation delivered at Ocean Best Practices Workshop, online, on 17 October 2024. Part of the session "Ocean-Climate Nexus - Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points, and the downstream effects of Tipping Points." organized jointly by TipESM, OCEAN:ICE, ClimTip and ObsSea4Clim EU Horizon projects.

Uploaded on December 5, 2024
Part of TipESM, EU Open Research Repository

Why use Zenodo?

- **Safe** — your research is stored safely for the future in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists.
- **Trusted** — built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE to ensure that everyone can join in Open Science.
- **Citeable** — every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), to make them citable and trackable.
- **No waiting time** — Uploads are made available online as soon as you hit publish, and your DOI is registered within seconds.
- **Open or closed** — Share e.g. anonymized clinical trial data with only medical professionals via our restricted access mode.
- **Versioning** — Easily update your dataset with our versioning feature.
- **GitHub integration** — Easily preserve your GitHub repository in Zenodo.
- **Usage statistics** — All uploads display standards compliant usage statistics

Newsletter

Receive updates on our latest developments, projects and upcoming webinars sent quarterly.

E-mail *
your-email@example.com

Name
Your name

Subscribe

When uploading your files, you have the option to add them to our institutional community at Zenodo. To do so, you must click on the blue field written "**Select a community**".

Alternatively, you can choose to upload files without associating them with the IQTC community, instead storing them in your personal space. To do this, simply follow the upload procedure without selecting a community during the process.

If you chose to select a community, in the search field write down:

"Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional"

Then select the IQTC community to be associated to your upload by clicking on "Select".

Now, you must start by uploading the files you wish by clicking on the blue box "Upload files" or by dragging and dropping to the gray area as many files as you want.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo upload interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and user information. Below this, the 'Files' tab is active, indicated by a red arrow. The main area shows a 'Drag and drop files' instruction and a red-bordered 'Upload files' button. To the right, a 'Draft' panel contains 'Save draft', 'Preview', 'Submit for review', and 'Share' buttons. Below the 'Files' section, the 'Basic information' section is visible, featuring a 'Digital Object Identifier' field, a 'Do you already have a DOI for this upload?' question, a 'Resource type' dropdown, a 'Title' field, a 'Publication date' field, and a 'Creators' field. The 'Visibility' section shows 'Public' selected, with a note that 'The record and files are publicly accessible.' and an option to 'Apply an embargo'.

After uploading the files, you must decide about the **Visibility** of the files, if you want it **Public** or **Restricted**. Additionally, in the "Basic information" session, you must fill the fields with the related metadata. For instance, the fields **DOI**, **Resource type**, **Title**, **Publication date**, **Creators** are mandatory.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo upload interface. At the top, there is a blue header with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below the header, the user's profile 'jjonathan...' is visible. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Files:** A section for uploading files, showing 'Storage available: 0 out of 100 files, 0 bytes out of 50.00 GB'. It includes a 'Drag and drop files' area and an 'Upload files' button.
- Basic information:** A section for entering metadata, highlighted with a red arrow. It includes:
 - Digital Object Identifier:** A field for entering a DOI, with a 'Yes' radio button selected.
 - Resource type:** A dropdown menu.
 - Title:** A text input field.
 - Publication date:** A date input field set to '2024-12-05'.
 - Creators:** A section for adding creators.
- Visibility:** A section for setting the visibility of the files, highlighted with a red arrow. It includes:
 - Files only:** A dropdown menu with 'Public' selected.
 - Options:** A section for applying an embargo.

To improve file discoverability and identification, all uploads on Zenodo must be assigned a DOI. If your upload already has a DOI, select "**YES**" and enter the existing DOI. If it does not, select "**NO**", and Zenodo will generate a unique DOI specifically for your submission.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo upload interface. At the top, there is a 'Files' section with a blue header and a right-pointing arrow. Below this, a storage status bar indicates 'Storage available' with '0 out of 100 files' and '0 bytes out of 50.00 GB'. A large dashed box contains the text 'Drag and drop files' and '- or -' followed by an 'Upload files' button with an upward arrow icon.

The 'Basic information' section has a blue header with a right-pointing arrow. Below it, the 'Digital Object Identifier' section is highlighted with a red border. It contains the following elements:

- A heading: **Digital Object Identifier**
- A question: 'Do you already have a DOI for this upload?' with two radio buttons: 'Yes' (selected) and 'No'.
- A text input field with the placeholder text 'Copy/paste your existing DOI here...'
- A small explanatory text: 'A DOI allows your upload to be easily and unambiguously cited. Example: 10.1234/foo.bar'

Below the DOI section are two dropdown menus: 'Resource type' and 'Title'.

On the right side of the interface, there is a 'Draft' section with a dropdown arrow. It contains buttons for 'Save draft', 'Preview', 'Publish', and 'Share'. Below this is the 'Visibility' section, which has a heading and a sub-section 'Files only' with two radio buttons: 'Public' (selected) and 'Restricted'. A green box with a lock icon and the text 'Public The record and files are publicly accessible.' is visible. At the bottom of the right sidebar, there is an 'Options' section with a link 'Apply an embargo' and a note: 'Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.'

In the "Creators" field, you must list all individuals involved in creating/producing the file you are uploading. To add a creator, click on "**Add Creator**" and search for them using their name, identifier (e.g., ORCID), or affiliation. If the creator cannot be found, ensure you manually fill in at least the following fields: **FAMILY NAME**, **GIVEN NAMES**, **IDENTIFIERS**, and **ROLE**. As you are the uploader, you should include yourself in the list of creators. When finished to include all creators, click on "**Save**".

The image shows a screenshot of the Zenodo website's "Add creator" modal form. The form is titled "Add creator" and has two radio buttons at the top: "Person" (selected) and "Organization". Below this is a search bar with the placeholder text "Search for persons by name, identifier, or affiliation...". The form is divided into several sections: "Family name" with a text input field containing "FAMILY NAME"; "Given names" with a text input field containing "NAME"; "Identifiers" with a text input field containing "e.g. ORCID, ISNI or GND."; "Affiliations" with a dropdown menu containing "Search or create affiliation"; and "Role" with a dropdown menu containing "Researcher". At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: "Cancel", "Save and add another", and "Save". The background of the screenshot shows the Zenodo interface with a dark header and a sidebar on the left.

To improve the documentation of your uploads, more metadata can be inserted in the additional fields **RECOMMENDED INFORMATION**, **FUNDING**, **ALTERNATIVE IDENTIFIERS** and **RELATED WORKS**. Information such as **Contributors**, **Awards/Grants** and **Related works** can be associated to your uploads.

Recommended information

Contributors
+ Add contributor

Keywords and subjects
Search for a subject by name

Languages
Search for a language by name (e.g "eng", "fr" or "Polish")

Dates

Date *	Type *	Description
YYYY-MM-DD or YYYY-MM-DD/YYYY-MM-DD		

Format: DATE or DATE/DATE where DATE is YYYY or YYYY-MM or YYYY-MM-DD.

+ Add date

Version

Mostly relevant for software and dataset uploads. A semantic version string is preferred see semver.org, but any version string is accepted.

Publisher
Zenodo

The publisher is used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.

Funding

Awards/Grants
+ Add + Add custom

Alternate identifiers

Identifier *	Scheme *

+ Add identifier

Related works

Specify identifiers of related works. Supported identifiers include DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, ISSN, ISBN, PubMed ID, PubMed Central ID, ADS Bibliographic Code, arXiv, Life Science Identifiers (LSID), EAN-13, ISTD, URNs, and URLs.

Relation *	Identifier *	Scheme *	Resource type
Select relation...			

+ Add related work

Draft

Save draft Preview

Submit for review

Share

Visibility

Files only

Public Restricted

Public
The record and files are publicly accessible.

Options

Apply an embargo
Record or files protection must be restricted to apply an embargo.

Once filled all fields that you think is necessary, you can **Preview**, save as **Draft** or **Submit for review**. If you have chose to upload your file to the IQTC community, click on "**Submit for Review**" to send your upload for approval by the IQTC community moderators on Zenodo. If you are not associating your upload with the our community, simply click on "**Publish**" to complete the process.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo upload interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. The user is logged in as 'rosadesou...'. Below the header, the community 'iqtc Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional' is selected. The main area is titled 'Files' and shows a table with one file: 'blankpage.pdf' (1.17 KB, 100% progress). To the right of the file list, there are buttons for 'Save draft', 'Preview', 'Submit for review', and 'Share'. The 'Submit for review' button is highlighted with a red box. Below the file list, there is a 'Drag and drop files' area and a warning message: 'File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload.' The 'Basic information' section includes a 'Digital Object Identifier' field with 'Yes' and 'No' radio buttons, a 'Resource type' dropdown set to 'Other', a 'Title' field with 'blankpage', and a 'Publication date' field with '2024-12-05'. The 'Creators' section shows 'R. Souza, Jhonathan'.

3 Finding IQTC community in the Zenodo platform

If you want to follow the research activities and files uploaded by the IQTC community, you must copy and paste the following link to your browser. You will be directed to the IQTC community page into Zenodo platform.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/iqtc-ub/>

Another option is simply to search for the community inside the Zenodo. On your home page, click on "**Communities**". Then, write "**Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional**" on the **Search community** field.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and tabs for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. A red arrow points to the 'Communities' tab. Below the navigation bar, the main content area is titled 'Communities' and includes a search bar with the text 'Institut de química teòrica i computacional' and a green 'New community' button. The page is divided into sections: 'Featured communities' with a card for 'The Generic Mapping Tools' and 'New communities' with five cards: 'EMPYREAN EU Horizon (101136...', 'Dagstuhl Publishing', 'Interoperable open-source T...', 'Games and Learning Alliance...', and 'INPACE Hub'.

Next, click on the institute's name to access the IQTC page on Zenodo.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo Communities page. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'institut de química teòrica i computacional' and a search icon. To the right of the search bar, there are options for 'Sort by' (set to 'Best match') and a 'New community' button. Below the search bar, the search results are displayed. The first result is 'Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional', which is highlighted with a red box. This result includes the IQTC logo, the name of the institute, a brief description, and links to its website and the University of Barcelona. Below this result, there are several other community entries, each with a logo and a title: 'QComp - Boletim de Química Computacional', 'CAA Deutschland - Computeranwendungen und Quantitative Methoden in der Archäologie', 'Chirality And Spin selectiVity in eLectron transfER processes: From quantum detection to quantum enabled technologies', 'Informática y Sistemas: Revista de Tecnologías de la Informática y las Comunicaciones', 'CiTIUS- Centro Singular de Investigación en Tecnologías Intelixenteas da Universidade de Santiago de Compostela', and 'Artefatos da Pesquisa "Fatores que Influenciam a Participação Feminina em Competições de Programação"'. On the left side of the page, there are filters for 'Type' (Project, Organization, Topic, Event) and 'Funders' (European Commission, European Union, UK Research and Innovation, U.S. National Science Foundation, Agencia Estatal de Investigación, Ministerio para la Transformación Digital y de la Función Pública, National Agency for Research, Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades, Foundation for Science and Technology, German Research Foundation). At the bottom of the page, there is a page number '17'.

On this page, you can track the status of your uploaded files and explore other uploads shared by members of the IQTC community.

The screenshot displays the Zenodo interface for the IQTC community. At the top, there is a blue header with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below the header, the community name 'Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional' is shown, along with its website URL and affiliation with the University of Barcelona. A 'New upload' button is visible in the top right. The main content area features a search bar and a message: 'We couldn't find any matches for your search'. To the left, there are options for 'Versions' (with a 'View all versions' toggle) and 'Help' (with a 'Search guide' link). A 'ProTip!' box contains the following text: 'metadata.publication_date:[2017-01-01 TO *]' will give you all the publications from 2017 until today. For more tips, check out our search guide for defining advanced search queries.